

A STUDY ON PARTNERING FOR SUSTAINABILITY IN THE WORKPLACE

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ABSTRACT

There is nothing very sustainable about many workplaces. Doing something about it can be expensive, but even when large sums have been spent on design and construction, much of the benefit relies on the cooperation of staff. A more sustainable strategy than the capital investment alone is to make the workplace more sustainable in the way employees operate in it. More specifically, the key to enduring and efficient work practices that minimise resource use and waste while maximising well-being, is the nurturing of partnerships between the building managers and the workers. The Author explores this assertion in relation to the social dynamics in the typical office high-rise. The relationship between office building landlords and occupants has traditionally been confined to financial negotiations over rent and services. This almost inevitably combative arrangement which has contributed to the demands for ‘quiet enjoyment’ of leases and has significantly retarded the development of stakeholder partnerships so central to the sustainable outcomes. The Author argues that the creation of an efficient, productive and rewarding high-rise office atmosphere pivots on disclosure of knowledge, ideas and data, and lubricated by trust, transparency and accountable governance. Without the free flow of information, effective feedback loops and education programmes, office workers will remain disconnected from building management.

KEYWORDS: communication; disclosure; governance; knowledge; partnership; post-occupancy evaluation; sustainability; trust.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability is a powerful buzzword for a good reason. It is strongly connected to notions of endurance, flexibility, quality assurance and alternative thinking – all of which are emerging as building blocks of financially successful enterprise. Therefore, there is no surprise that the recently released “Stern Review on the Economics of Climate Change” (Stern, 2006) emphasises

the potential financial opportunities for those who take advantage of climate change by out-competing less sustainability savvy operators. It is the prevalence of this type of thinking that in itself gives us our first clue to how sustainable workplaces and practices are being conceptualised and shaped by industry. They are increasingly being seen as the efforts and initiatives taking place in a climate changing world that make business more resilient and often more profitable by what they do, rather than what they make the market do. In other words, the market is framing sustainability responses rather than sustainability processes framing the market.

Implicit in this view of sustainability in action, but clearly less well-understood, is the exercise of greater social responsibility by employers in terms of equity, access, and employee engagement within the confines of what few enterprises appear to realise are social systems constrained by limits (Hirsch, 1977). Given this gap in our collective knowledge, then it is reasonable to assume that exploring the social dimensions of the economic ‘opportunities’ of climate change represents attractive low hanging fruit. In this respect, we are guided by Hirsch’s hypothesis that “...as the level of average consumption rises, an increasing portion of consumption takes on a social as well as individual aspect” (Hirsch, 1977, p.2). The problem is, as Hirsch observed, that the distributions of the benefits of production are increasingly intertwined with questions about what, how much, and on what basis goods and services are produced. This means that the distribution of workplace productivity returns should not only address social needs, but also these needs should be increasingly met through the provision and collective engendering of a suite of non-financial benefits. This article discusses what this might mean in the office high-rise workplace.

At first, the article explores some of the ‘instrumental arrangements’ that are beginning to influence the high-rise office workplace. In particular, the rise of the green building is discussed along with the emergence of building environmental rating systems, and to a lesser extent, green leases. This is useful background for understanding the ‘institutional arrangements’ that are beginning to shape at least some of the social interactions taking place in the high-rise office space. These new ‘partnering institutions’ arguably have the potential to change building if not sector governance by establishing the information-rich ‘knowledge conduits’ that help to build capacity within the work environment. Finally, it is suggested that partnering for sustainability is not only a comparatively inexpensive route towards a more satisfying and efficient workplace, but also a likely to fundamentally reshape accompanying and future financial investment in environmental initiatives.

In short, this discussion finds that a sustainable workplace hinges on human compatibility and employee as well as employer input, which in turn relies significantly on the ‘institutional’ environment, or more simply, the ‘rules of the game’. When those rules are clearly focused on sustainable outcomes, this ‘new institutionalism’ can reduce transaction costs understood as environmental externalities (North, 1990, 1992). And ultimately, these rules are both devised and observed within the social realm. Institutions (rules) are not made of bricks and mortar, but use bricks and mortar to facilitate social activity. Thus, the proposition put here is that there are limits to the sustainability processes that are enabled by the built form, and these can be only exceeded, and indeed, redefined, through social reform within the workplace.

THE VALUE OF SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY

Hall and Pfeiffer (2000) have convincingly argued that the hardware in which we work and live is increasingly becoming less attuned to our needs, wants, and wishes. They observe that:

“Buildings in cities are always public because they create the communal environment; they are part of neighbourhoods and the physical basis for social networks. The ‘hardware city’ of infrastructure and buildings is interrelated with the ‘software city’ of habits, traditions, networks, markets and social relationships” (Hall and Pfeiffer, 2000, p.98).

This is a powerful analogy, explaining why there is a tendency to focus on the visible, while that which is not readily apparent escapes our attention. In other words, without users, buildings are only monumental in nature, and are deprived of much of their utilitarian meaning. Therefore, it is incomprehensible to try to understand the value of environmental initiatives in the workplace in isolation from people. Yet, the emerging green construction sector often does precisely this, approaching buildings as if they have a life of their own. The reality is that whether the workplace is viewed as a place which is characterised by social interaction, people remain at the core of both the obstacles and the solutions to increased sustainability.

The bias against the social side of sustainability is plain to see. Most efforts in the academic literature and in practice are clearly directed at the physical and economic aspects of sustainability, adding weight to the maxim that what gets measured gets reported. In this respect, a substantial body of research exists exploring energy saving, efficient water use, and waste management initiatives within commercially built assets. Perhaps even more problematic than prejudices against the intangible nature of social sustainability, however, are suspicions that such initiatives actively promote social interaction, resulting in falling productivity. In other words, it is often falsely assumed that social sustainability comes at a cost (implying physical works like common rooms, etc.) and delivers diminishing returns. However, anecdotal evidence at National@Docklands, where there are a great many spaces that encourage casual meetings, point to a reduction of expensive, and often administratively demanding, formal meetings than were undertaken at the occupants’ previous premises (Allenby, 2005). And, it would be interesting to look at a productivity study to see essentially what effect an increase in casual meetings has had. While anecdotal evidence abounds, empirical studies are seldom carried out using office accommodation as the variable. This will need to be addressed if social sustainability is to be taken seriously throughout the commercial property sector.

Even if the increased productivity is difficult to prove, the more widely accepted benefits of employee recruitment, workplace satisfaction, and ultimately staff retention, in a corporate climate that is increasingly measured in terms of the quality of employee contributions, eventually can be factored into rent review processes in premises that take social sustainability seriously, simply because tenants will be anxious to remain. This is an expression of the reputation component of a building at the worker level, while the reputation of buildings also operates at the all-important marketing level. And this significance of reputation explains why social sustainability has implications for the capitalised market value of a building.

An important lesson we have failed to learn from Hirsh is that: “Satisfactions from particular forms of work as well as from particular social or physical environments also need to be assessed because they influence the value attached to input and, therefore, to net output. The same output produced under more pleasant working conditions, whether these comprise more interesting work processes or longer coffee breaks, ought to be registered as larger net output. It represents the same gross output for less input” (Hirsch, 1977, p.16).

As early as the 1970s, leisure at work was “beginning to be recognised as a legitimate product of economic effort – on the important proviso that the work practices concerned are freely chosen in preference to more intensive work at higher rates of pay” (Hirsch, 1977, p.16). Yet mainstream economic accounting still records such behaviour as a productivity loss. However, the emerging discourse of social sustainability offers the most powerful critique of this conventional wisdom, and as empirically measured case study data becomes available, it is reasonable to assume that a widespread shift in thinking at the employer level is inevitable. The awarding of a Nobel Prize to Daniel Kahneman in 2002 for his contributions to behavioural economics that in part suggests precisely these types of things is further evidence that the economics establishment is being influenced by the accumulating research pointing to the benefits of work quality over work quantity (Kahneman, 2002).

GREEN BUILDINGS AND LEASES

Having briefly discussed the value of social sustainability in office buildings, the question Author now turn to is how social sustainability is actually delivered in the office high-rise workplace. The first point to emphasise here is that social sustainability is much more about process than capital works. Many architects, spruiking their credentials, are lining up to design green ‘hardware’. This is resulting in the penetration of green construction principles in the commercial building industry. New, the so-called green office high-rise buildings like Sydney’s The Bond, which earn many stars from various environmental accreditation schemes, are beginning to be built in and around Central Business Districts, while just about all new office buildings are now being designed and constructed with energy savings in mind. This is not just because this is a smart thing to do. Investors and developers are well aware that building codes are beginning to tighten, and expensive green retro-fits may be forced on owners in years to come, and this has value implications in today’s market.

Moreover, anecdotal evidence indicates that greener buildings are more marketable than traditional stock, and are providing the competitive edge in the battle to secure good long-term tenants. For example, Chris Kinder of commercial real estate agent Savills, the managing agent of Brisbane’s first 4½ star office high-rise, the William Buck Building, affirms that the building’s 12-month leasing-up period to high quality tenants was better than market average for new release office space. Meanwhile, energy savings were likely to be factored into the first round of rent reviews, providing returns for owners in excess of the market over the long term (Kinder, 2004). And just as the energy rating and labelling of white goods has improved efficiency, decreased emissions, and raised community expectations, the introduction of environmental rating systems for buildings should result in similar environmental benefits.

However, the Author is not so much concerned with constructing or modifying buildings for sustainability, as worthwhile as this is to do. Instead, Author focus on the more neglected and often mutually disconnected relationship between building managers and occupants. This is not to say that green construction does not take people into account. Clearly it does, and continues to make giant strides towards people-centred, socially responsible building innovations. What green construction proponents do not do very well though, simply because it has not got much to do with constructing the built form, is explore instruments that directly engage building stakeholders in projects that advance sustainability. Prominent amongst these initiatives are green leases and other financial arrangements that provide incentives to landlords to facilitate and encourage reductions in tenant outgoings and waste, and increases in efficiency.

Policy makers usually think in terms of incentives and regulatory, carrot and stick methods when planning for change. These approaches tend to be politically charged and seldom emerge from market dynamics. However, as the property industry is strongly driven by market demand, it makes good sense to design intrinsic market mechanisms to help to steer change more effectively and efficiently. Green leases are one such way for moving towards a more sustainable built environment in the commercial sector. Green leases are focused almost exclusively on human processes, and are not so much concerned with sustainable development understood in the narrow material sense. What is currently under-researched are the many less tangible environmentally and socially sensitive issues that are arguably of equal importance. As a concept, green leases seek to include all innovative measures that contribute to achieving a sustainable building.

Elaborating on Power (2004) and Roussac (2004), green leases:

Are owner-tenant agreements that recognise a standardised and desirable level of sustainability attaching to a specific premise, objectively measured by means of a sustainability index.

It can be established on premises that have favourable independent qualitative assessment. Such an assessment would be supported by a mixture of quantitative and qualitative data concerning its social and environmental performance that results in a collective (overall) ranking or sustainability index that exceeds the minimum required standard.

Are performance-based and are therefore subject to up- or down-grading from subsequent assessments. Any down-grading beyond the minimum standard would strip a lease of its green status. Conversely, an up-grading of a sustainability index may award the premises a green rating.

Not only take into account a building's draw on resources and its emissions and waste, but also they express an appreciation for ecologically sensitive design, wider planning implications and governance performance. Green leases imply that the right managerial decisions are being made to advance sustainability and that systematic stakeholder capacity building and participation is being encouraged.

Have clearly articulated guidelines pertaining to the operations, maintenance and procedures undertaken, and recognise that there is a complex information chain that must be closely monitored.

Specify that owners, managers and occupants all have distinct obligations to fulfil. Failure to comply with obligations at any level could potentially result in the downgrading of a building's sustainability index.

Are not only designed to be environmentally friendly, but also they grounded on the notion of economic sustainability. This is understood as sustained economic returns given an investment horizon that is likely to be increasingly characterised by tighter environmental controls and rising demand for space that contributes to reputation enhancement, user-friendliness, productivity and occupant well-being.

Are inevitably based on the performance of indicators that will vary depending on a number of factors such as asset type, utility and locality, which may change over time according to the social and political climate.

Perhaps above all, emphasise the importance of processes involved in sustainability strategies rather than specific desired outcomes. These processes hinge on the commitment of owners, adequate transparency and disclosure from management, and the clarity of responses from occupants. Ideally, green leases are characterised by a virtuous cycle of information for effective and continuous learning.

Essentially, green leases are a binding agreement between owners and tenants of office buildings recognising that the workspace has attained a certain standard of sustainability. They obligate both managers and occupants to continue to satisfy requirements that maintain sustainability at a high level. Green leases also carry with them a level of prestige that is reputation-enhancing for all stakeholders and for this reason may attract a premium rent in the market place. Leading office owner and manager Investa, currently subject to a takeover from US-based Morgan Stanley Real Estate, are pioneering green leases in their existing stock, while such leases are also executed for new green buildings more widely. They work as a 'guarantee', with some leases stipulating that a fall in the environmental rating during tenancy can actually trigger a diminution in rent. For instance, the New South Wales Police Services have signed a lease with Multiplex for the Parramatta Headquarters declaring that the rent is to be reduced if its 4½ star rating falls (Dorfling, 2004).

While green leases are being experimented with in new green buildings, Investa is finding that it also have much untapped potential to help to generate sustainability in existing stocks (Roussac, 2004). Relying more on social capital than capital expenditure to improve sustainability outcomes, this new approach is particularly attractive to owners who currently have few financial incentives for sponsoring efficiencies that result in reduced tenant outgoings. However, a key initiative in the establishment of green leases is the embrace of post-occupancy building evaluations, which to date have had a chequered role to play for reasons that will be explained later.

Green leases are only one of a number of instruments being explored by sustainability-minded owners and tenants. Most of these relate to innovative funding arrangements for the provision of energy saving devices. Publicly owned and large managed fund property portfolios, in particular, create economies of scale that support these types of improvements. For instance, the USA administration used enormous bargaining power and private sector partnerships to upgrade the energy efficiency of 500,000 Federal buildings. Likewise, the British government has implemented the Financing Renewable Energy and Efficiency programme in schools and hospitals, with private companies installing energy efficient lamps, air-conditioning systems and heating equipment at no cost.¹ In return, the installation companies receive part of the savings from the lower electricity bills for a designated number of years. For instance, a private company invested £2,000,000 to install a combined heat and power system in the Royal Liverpool hospital, providing energy savings estimated at £500,000 a year (Smith, Whitelegg and Williams, 1998). Financial initiatives are significantly less developed in Australia, but they are nevertheless an integral component of the National Greenhouse Strategy.

Such initiatives, whether financing energy efficiency directly or through third-party performance contracting, characterise ‘new public administrations’ in the way they are learning to work with the private sector to deliver public goods (Kimmert, 2003). It is precisely this ‘new institutionalism’ that needs to be transferred to ‘relational’ approaches to managing and occupying the commercial workplace. In brief, this means encouraging social engagement, limiting exclusion, widening disclosure, and screening out unethical influences.

James Grosse, who designed the ‘open hearted’ National@Docklands green building, explains that he conceptualises commercial buildings as ‘just a big house’ and even a ‘habitat’, because “after all, more than just being a piece of commercial architecture, an office is a place where people actually live during the day” (Allenby, 2005). His design was the result of a long consultative process with over 1,000 workers who would be occupying the building. And if consultation can play such a large part in the design stage, which is inevitably a technical process, there is no reason why it cannot achieve similar results when it comes to the culture and governance of a building.

THE PARTNERSHIP APPROACH

Having established that social sustainability has both economic and human value, and talked about non-material strategies like green lease agreements as a means to achieve it, attention will now be turned to disclosure as the central component in owner/manager tenant/worker partnerships. Business, and increasingly government, tend to base decisions on the economic return of investment, while internal knowledge building has been undervalued. However, knowledge of workplace operations, acquired largely from post-occupancy disclosure, is very important in decision-making for sustainability minded managers (Kimmert, 2004).

Like all investments, high-rise office buildings are assessed as a function of market ascribed worth (Boyd et al., 2004). Nevertheless, buildings are highly visible and have a reach far beyond the interests of investors and even their users by impacting communities in various ways. Furthermore, because buildings are the measurable physical entities, their impacts likewise

can be measured. However, as already explained, much of what is built is instrumental at its core and this utility reinforces the economic basis of building assessment – often, it would appear, to the exclusion of wider environmental implications. Nevertheless, effective governance of the non-material aspects of buildings improves functionality, enhances the human–building relationship, and helps to minimise negative environmental outcomes. In short, governance of a building can increase value simply by enhancing its appeal to existing as well as prospective tenants, and ultimately potential purchasers. Of course, the same can be said for the reverse. Ineffective governance can detract from the appeal of built assets, diminishing rental expectations and capitalised market value.

Rational economic discussions about the relationship between information, economic decision-making and prices in the modern era are strongly influenced by the approach of Friedrich Hayek in his classic article ‘The Use of Knowledge in Society’ (Hayek, 1945). This work is a useful starting point to draw out the implications that disclosure may have for the evaluation process. Hayek asserts that economic problems arise always and only in consequence of change, and claims that perfect knowledge reduces economic problems to a logical and mathematical form. Hayek (1945) is then quick to point out that this is ‘emphatically’ not the case in society simply because the relevant ‘data’ is never representative of the whole of society. Indeed, he describes this data as dispersed bits of incomplete and frequently contradictory knowledge possessed by separate individuals. The problem then with gaining increased efficiency, as Hayek sees it, is reduced to how knowledge is communicated to planners so as to allow the best possible decisions to be made. Hayek argues that the problem can either be solved by the decentralisation of decision-making to those with ‘hands on’ knowledge or by the price system. Hayek favours the price system because decentralisation introduces problems of its own in terms of cohesion.

However, because the social and environmental aspects of property are rarely accorded prices that fluctuate according to the market, the price system is not a valid option. Perhaps what can work instead of prices are values expressed as indicators (Lawn, 2001). These arbitrary indicators reflect human values more strongly than economic values, but are loaded with uncertainties about the consequences of action in relation to these values. Nevertheless it is this uncertainty that gives ethics and morality its form (Dawes, 1988).

While it can be assumed that human values are essentially ‘good’ and built asset indicators that take these values seriously can be expected to produce some sort of ‘benefit’, Kantian ethics urges us to endorse a set of ‘categorical imperatives’ irrespective of consequences. To overlay this philosophy on Hayek’s imperfect knowledge framework, we can conclude that optimal social benefits are derived when uninhibited communication is taking place concerning the performance of certain ethically-bound objectives. This leaves outcomes open-ended, and emphasises the importance of process and dialogue while deflecting the focus from the actual values and the data gathering exercises (Macneil et al., 1993). In short, it is ‘confronting the values realised with the values aimed at’ (de Beauvoir, 1948, p.152).

It is apparent then that the disclosure of individually acquired knowledge is a moral dilemma that brings about unknown consequences. To place this in the context of built assets, the discipline of environmental psychology is instructive. This field of study is premised on the idea “that every building has a set of purposes that can be defined in terms of human behaviour” (Lee, 1976, p.47). Accommodating this behaviour is contrary to the traditional overarching architectural priorities of aesthetic appeal, function, or some combination of both. As Lee pointed out in the mid-1970s when environmental psychology was in its infancy; “Although the textual material of evaluations (which is voluminous) now makes reference to how the building may be expected to ‘function’, it is rare to see any objective assessment of human response by the people actually using it” (Lee, 1976, p.45).

Bringing the human factor into the building performance context prompts us to revisit Hayek’s choice of a price system solution over decentralisation. Is it safe to assume that once dispersed, knowledge cannot be cohesively and comprehensively gathered up and delivered to decision-makers? The reasoning followed in this discussion suggests that Hayek may well be right if analysing the values themselves is made the priority – in other words, if decision-makers are located where knowledge about a particular value is most complete. On the other hand, there is much promise in processes being put in place that promote the flow of information from above, particularly concerning what values are important. And building performance could be further enhanced if users are encouraged to divulge their responses to such values, with the total sum of knowledge disclosed to independent appraisers.

DISCLOSURE AND GOVERNANCE

Governance clearly influences economic sustainability. In a supportive environment, efficient and effective governance can eliminate costly short-sightedness, corruption, hazardous and inefficient practices, while it also has a hand in reputation building. In keeping with new administrative and institutional frameworks, disclosure informed governance is a public good, and should be approached from that perspective. Governance is about making the right managerial decisions. This requires systematic capacity building within the wider decision-making apparatus, participation from as many stakeholders as possible, and the clear enunciation of guidelines pertaining to the operations, maintenance and procedures undertaken. Inadequate, under-specified and especially unarticulated instructions, actions, performance or feedback anywhere along this complex information chain can result in sub-optimum outcomes in terms of building performance.

In relation to external assessments, basic economic data on buildings is readily available or obtainable, allowing conventional assessments to be undertaken. This situation, however, is contrasted by the relative inaccessibility of social and environmental performance data. The quality and accuracy of this type of data obtained from a physical inspection and from outside sources is often limited. Without honest and detailed disclosure of social and environmental records from the building users and managers, governance will lack substance and credibility. Of course, data and assessments may not even be available, meaning that the acquisition of systematic measurements and quality feedback is an important part of the disclosure process. But

while there is a significant amount of research going on that is aimed at providing tools for gathering information on buildings, discussions about the benefits of making this data public and how it can be done are seldom heard.

Disclosure does not come naturally in the relatively secretive world of property investment, and this is where governance reforms play an important role. These reforms are not so much focused on changing the way business is done; it is schooling stakeholders in the value of transparency. As a consequence, this heightened awareness of the benefits of ‘openness’ is effecting normative changes in society that are beginning to impact the market in terms of supply and demand factors. In the built environment, this is demonstrated by construction that is more environmentally sensitive than has previously been the case. It is also likely to lead to more socially sustainable buildings (Kimmet, 2003).

Post-occupancy building performance analysis has taken place randomly since the 1950s for marketing purposes, and refers to survey practices and processes of buildings in use. Such surveys became more systematic in the 1970s, however, monitoring building performance remains a neglected and, at best, piecemeal and subjective task with little priority. In recent years though, the Probe project in the UK has streamlined survey methods, making them more cost-effective and manageable, and improving their applicability and usefulness (Leaman and Bordass, 2004). The project sponsored the procurement of data from 20 individual buildings in use from 1997 to 2002. Probe’s findings are manifold, and underscore the complex and fundamental linkages between quality feedback and improved usability of buildings.

For instance, principal researchers involved in the project found that: “Feedback systems must not just be imposed from above but be useful to those actually working on projects. Effective techniques are already available, some with good track records. IT and the internet are making them faster, more powerful, more economical, easier to use, and providing more reliable statistics and benchmarks. We need to make good use of the results. Feedback data needs to be managed in order to lead to effective learning. But data and knowledge management tends to be a weak spot for most organisations, even purveyors of feedback techniques.” (Bordass et al., 2004, p.13).

These observations highlight the centrality of disclosure as a mechanism to devolve under-informed decision-making from above and to energise systems designed to spawn and then trawl through feedback. Such feedback needs to be impartial and reliable, something that analysts with an interest in obtaining favourable reports find very difficult to do. Clearly it is the “bad news ... [where in] the greatest part of the scope for rapid improvement actually lies” (Leaman and Bodmass, 2004, p.11). This highlights the need for transparent disclosure to independent assessment teams, with their findings feeding back directly to those decision makers involved at each stage of the building life cycle.

Establishing benchmarks predicated on disclosure of performance data is a systematic way of structuring feedback. Benchmarks based on objectives provide a material target, even when the particular focus may at first seem quite intangible. This is often the case with social criteria, such as stakeholder involvement, community engagement, occupier satisfaction and

cultural issues. Hence, the more appropriate, sensitive and clearly articulated the benchmarks are, the more routine do the quality control management practices become, stimulating continuous learning based on measurable outcomes (Leaman and Bodmass, 2004).

A major obstacle to surveying tenants has not only been the failure to recognise the importance of building user surveys, but also a perception that owners and occupants view the process as time-consuming and invasive, detracting from their quiet enjoyment of the premises. What needs to be understood, more than anything, which may help to emancipate post-occupancy evaluation from the expectations of quiet enjoyment, is that the processes involved in providing adequate responses to user surveys are more important than the actual data itself. It is these processes that stakeholders must focus on if social sustainability is to be genuinely pursued.

In Australia, post-occupancy building evaluations are very much in their infancy. What this paper aims to advance, therefore, is the level of importance placed on understanding why and how social sustainability initiatives impact on the value of buildings – which will increase demand for post-occupancy evaluations. And it will also elevate civics as a predictor of economics, debunking assumptions that markets operate in some sort of vacuum, impervious to the constantly evolving normative structures within society (Putnam, 1993).

CONCLUSION

The ultimate outcome of post-occupancy evaluations is the creation of virtuous cycles for effective and continuous learning and trust building. Indeed, if we are to treat the construction and management of built assets as the science that it clearly has become, then we will increasingly see the role of appraisal and information feedback loops in the same way as we view the testing and validation of a scientific experiment. It will exert moral obligation on management “to learn from successes and mistakes, to eschew what Wools (1970) has called the ‘cuckoo mentality’ in which office buildings are laid like eggs in the nests of others (often fund managers), and then hopefully abandoned” (Lee, 1976, p.48).

Information is knowledge, and when fully disclosed, provides the building blocks for a whole new architecture – architecture of effective and efficient governance demonstrated in the first instance by the innovative use of glass and cement, site and place, and purpose and structure. This architecture remains fundamentally incomplete if the governance of a building does not build trust between owners and tenants, without which partnerships for sustainability simply cannot be sustained.

Getting people to live differently – i.e. sustainably – involve changing values, attitudes, expectations and, most of all, behaviour. Traditional ‘top-down’ approaches where a content expert downloads on a passive audience are not generally successful in bringing about such changes. Nor is it sufficient to provide information on what is ‘right’ in which whatever form of media is used. ‘Knowing’ the right thing is not ‘doing’ the right thing. Many people are already aware of the changes needed to live more sustainably. Frameworks of communication and trust that facilitate a transition from awareness to action are needed.

Communication for socially sustainable buildings must deal with the wider challenges sustainability presents, such as:

Workers are generally content with their unsustainable behaviour

Rewards and savings from sustainability are often delayed and indirect

Behaviour change can be slow, so messages need to be sustained

Target audiences range from young adults to company directors, all with different motivators and understandings of sustainability and its implications

Sustainability is a complex issue incorporating environmental, social and economic factors

Experts are more familiar communicating with management than with users

There are disparate and unformed views of what a socially sustainable building looks like and how it can be acquired.

Communication that brings about the social changes required for sustainability tends to be more effective if it comes from trusted, credible sources such as work colleagues in informal social settings. It aims for an exchange of ideas with the goal of a shared understanding, affording ownership of what has been communicated rather than imparting one-sided rational arguments. Once people are excited, engaged, enabled and empowered by what they have heard or seen, they are motivated to pass it on, becoming powerful agents of further change. Innovative strategies grounded on partnership approaches exist that can help to cultivate social sustainability in buildings relatively cheaply. Communicating what are essentially communication strategies is the first crucial step taken here.

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